

Evaluation of efficacy and safety of intravenous hydralazine vs. labetalol in pregnancy related hypertension.

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Abstract:

Objective: The aim of this study was to evaluate the efficacy and safety of intravenous hydralazine in comparison with labetalol in pregnancy related hypertension.

Place and Duration of Study: This study was carried out in a duration of 9 months from February 2019 to October 2019 in medical departments of Indus hospital Karachi.

Study type: Comparative study.

Materials and methods: A total of 152 patients were selected for this study and two groups were formed. One was hydralazine group and other was labetalol group. Initial reading of blood pressure was done followed by a dose of hydralazine in one group and labetalol in other group. After that side effects, dose and time required to achieve the desired blood pressure was noted.

Results: 69.5% of the patients in hydralazine group achieved the required blood pressure with the 1st dose. Significantly higher number of 81.5% was seen in case of labetalol group who achieved desired blood pressure with 1st dose. Results of our study showed that rapid control of blood pressure is achieved with labetalol as compared to hydralazine. Side effects were also noted in both groups.

Conclusion: It was concluded from our study that both drugs were efficient in decreasing the blood pressure in pregnancy related hypertension to desired levels. However, labetalol is superior and more efficient in decreasing blood pressure as compared to hydralazine.

Keywords: Hydralazine, Labetalol, Pregnancy related hypertension.

Introduction: Pregnancy related hypertension is a common and serious medical disorder. Almost 10-15% pregnancies are affected by severe hypertension leading to high neonatal and maternal morbidity and mortality. Pregnant women with severe hypertension with systolic blood pressure 160mmHg or diastolic blood pressure 110mmHg

carry high risk for fetal disorders. Cerebral hemorrhage is a serious condition resulting from hypertension leading to maternal death. With proper control of blood pressure maternal mortality rate can be decreased. Aim should focused on reducing the blood pressure to diastolic levels below 110mmHg and that of systolic below 160mmHg. Aim of our study was to find a drug suitable to reduce blood pressure in pregnancy and with minimum side effects. Our study included hydralazine and labetalol. Hydralazine causes peripheral vasodilation by relaxing vascular smooth muscles and thus resulting in decreased blood pressure. Duration of onset is 10-20 minutes and effects lasts for 3 to 8 hours. IV hydralazine can cause hypotension and it is advisable to give prophylactic crystalloid solution to avoid hypotension. Alpha-1-adrenergic receptors are present in vascular smooth muscles and labetalol binds competitively with these receptors and inhibits vasoconstriction. Duration of onset in 5 minutes and effect lasts for 3-6 hours.

Materials and Methods: Patients the 28th week of gestation and with pregnancy induced hypertension were selected for this study. Patients with other diseases like heart problems, asthma or allergy to medication were not included in this study. Informed consent was taken from all the patients after detailed explanation. Ethical committee approval was taken.

A total of 152 patients were selected for this study and two groups were formed. One was hydralazine group and other was labetalol group. Initial reading of blood pressure was done followed by a dose of hydralazine in one group and labetalol in other group. After that side effects, dose and time required to achieve the desired blood pressure was noted.

140-150mmHg was the targeted systolic BP and 90-100 was the targeted diastolic BP. 1st dose was given and the reading of the blood pressure was done and dose repeated if needed. If the 1st dose was inadequate in controlling BP then 2nd dose was given along with 10mg of nifedipine.

Hydralazine group: Initially oral 5mg of hydralazine was given and reading of BP was done after 20 minutes. In case of failure to achieve the desired BP 10mg dose was given and reading of BP was done after 20 minutes. In cases where desired BP was not achieved, 20mg hydralazine was given along with 10mg nifedipine followed by a reading of BP. High blood pressure after these measures was controlled by medication as per advice. After every 10 minutes heart rate was calculated. Fetal heart rate was checked every 30 minutes.

Labetalol group: initially oral 20mg labetalol was given and reading of BP was done after 10 minutes. In case of failure to achieve the desired BP 40mg labetalol was given and reading of BP was done after 10 minutes. In case where desired BP was not achieved, 80 mg labetalol was given along with 10 mg nifedipine followed by a reading of BP. High blood pressure after these measures was controlled by medication as per advice.

SPSS version 21 was used to analyze the data.

Results: 69.5% of the patients in hydralazine group achieved the required blood pressure with the 1st dose. Significantly higher number of 81.5% was seen in case of labetalol group who achieved desired blood pressure with 1st dose. Results of our study showed that rapid control of blood pressure is achieved with labetalol as compared to hydralazine. Side effects were also noted in both groups.

Table 1 shows mean blood pressure of hydralazine group and labetalol group.

Blood pressure in mm hg	Hydralazine group n = 76 (%)	Labetalol group n = 76 (%)	P value (unpaired t test)
Systolic blood pressure	71 (93.4)	66 (86.8)	
160–180			
181–200	4 (5.3)	9 (11.9)	
[201	1 (1.3)	1 (1.3)	
Mean ± SD	169.6 ± 11.7	172.3 ± 12.6	0.17
Diastolic blood pressure	39 (51.3)	44 (57.8)	
80–100			
101–110	29 (38.2)	23 (30.3)	
111–120	7 (9.2)	9 (11.9)	
[120	1 (1.3)	–	
Mean ± SD	105.6 ± 8.36	104.6 ± 8.23	0.45
Mean arterial pressure	28 (36.8)	19 (25)	
110–120			
121–130	28 (36.8)	43 (56.6)	
131–140	16 (21)	7 (9.2)	
[140	4 (5.4)	7 (9.2)	
Mean ± SD	126.94 ± 7.99	127.15 ± 8.15	0.8

Table 2 shows the number of doses required to control the BP

Number of doses	Hydralazine group n=76%	Labetalol group N=76%	P value
1	53 (69.7%)	62 (81.5%)	0.04
2	23 (30.3%)	12 (15.8%)	
3		2 (2.7%)	

Table 3 shows time required to achieve the desired blood pressure.

Time in minutes	Hydralazine group n=76%	Labetalol group N=76%	P value
10	1 (1.3)	62 (81.5)	
20	52 (68.3)	12 (15.8)	
40	21 (21.7)	-	
50	2 (2.7)	2 (2.7)	
Mean ± SD (95% CI)	26.32±9.78 (24.08-28.55)	12.63±7.19 (10.99-14.27)	0.0001

Discussion: It has been shown in previous studies that hydralazine can lead to maternal hypotension. Other side effects like flushing, headache, nausea and tachycardia were the common side effects seen with the use of hydralazine whereas these side effects are less likely with the use of labetalol. Table 4 shows comparison of side effects of hydralazine and labetalol.

Table 4:

	Hydralazine group n = 76 (%)	Labetalol group n = 76 (%)	P value (comparison of proportion)	Fisher's exact test
Headache	2 (2.7)	3 (3.9)	0.97	1 (NS)
Nausea	2 (2.7)	-		1 (NS)
Vomiting	-	2 (2.7)		0.49 (NS)
Visual disturbances	1 (1.3)	-		1 (NS)
Additional drug required	2 (2.7)	2 (2.7)		1 (NS)
Persistent hypertension	2 (2.7)	3 (3.9)	0.97	1 (NS)
Convulsion after drug administration	3 (3.9)	1 (1.3)	0.62	0.61 (NS)
Maternal hypotension	1 (1.3)	-		1 (NS)
Maternal tachycardia	-	1 (1.3)		1 (NS)

Pregnancy related hypertension is a common and serious medical disorder. Almost 10-15% pregnancies are affected by severe hypertension leading to high neonatal and maternal morbidity and mortality. Pregnant women with severe hypertension with systolic blood pressure 160mmHg or diastolic blood pressure 110mmHg carry high risk for fetal disorders. Cerebral hemorrhage is a serious condition resulting from hypertension leading to maternal death. With proper control of blood pressure maternal mortality rate can be decreased. Aim should be focused on reducing the blood pressure to diastolic levels below 110mmHg and that of systolic below 160mmHg.

A study was conducted by Sharma et al with 100 female patients among which hydralazine was given to 69 patients and labetalol was given to 31

patients. 30 percent decrease in systolic BP was seen and was comparable in hydralazine (11%) group and labetalol group (10%). Nombur et al showed that for treating preeclampsia either hydralazine or labetalol can be used depending on the familiarity of the physician with the drug. This is in contrast to our study.

According to our study headache was more common in patients using hydralazine as compared to labetalol. No significant difference was seen in fetal activity in both groups.

Conclusion: It was concluded from our study that both drugs were efficient in decreasing the blood pressure in pregnancy related hypertension to desired levels. However, labetalol is superior and more efficient in decreasing blood pressure as compared to hydralazine.

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